

Evolution History of Chinese Han Nationality Reflect Great Integration of Chinese Nation

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ABSTRACT: Based on the importance, necessity and feasibility of the great integration of Chinese Nation, this paper expounds the concept and origin of Nation. On this basis, the origin of the Han Nationality, the evolution of the Han Nationality carried on the historical retrospection and the historical context, the evolution of the Han Nationality was elaborated in detail. The evolution characteristics of the Han Nationality are analyzed in detail, pointing out that the Han Nationality originated from the Huaxia Nationality, dating back to the middle and upper reaches of the Yellow River during the period of Three Emperors and five emperors. According to the development of time, in the long course of history, the Han Nationality had constantly blended and integrated with the surrounding residents in the process of development. Through detailed analysis, it had been found that the Han nationality and other ethnic minorities in China share the same root, same origin, same ancestor and same lineage, which provides the theoretical basis and practical historical facts for the great integration of the Chinese nation. It provides historical evidence for the feasibility, importance and urgency of the great integration of the Chinese nation.

KEYWORDS: Evolution history; Great integration of Chinese Nation, Han Nationality.

1. INTRODUCTION

China was an ancient country with a history of thousands or even thousands of years of civilization, but it was customary to say that the history of Chinese civilization would be more than 5,000 years, and this history of civilization was not forged by a single nation, but by all the Chinese descendants and people of other ethnic groups. Throughout the history of China and the history of Chinese civilization, various ethnic groups on the land of China had contacted, interacted with and integrated with each other, and had experienced five major ethnic integration, and finally formed a harmonious situation in which China's 56 ethnic groups share life and death, honor and shame, and destiny. The eighteenth Congress of Chinese Communist Party had put forward the concept of Chinese nation community and the thought and theory of identity, and once again emphasized the importance and great significance of ethnic unity and the great integration of Chinese nation, which had aroused the interest and enthusiasm of the majority of Chinese scientific researchers in the study of ethnic integration.

2. ETHNIC CONCEPT AND ORIGIN

However, neither the Hans nor their ancestors, the Huaxia Nationality People, or even these earlier people, never gave their names to what ethnic title they were given, and the title of the Hans should have been finally established during the late Qing Dynasty to the Republic of China, with the rise of Chinese nationalism. The document [1] had believed that the emergence of "Han nationality" originated from the Opium War and the invasion of the foreign powers in late Qing Dynasty, and the survival crisis of the country and the nation had awakened the unprecedented awakening of the national consciousness of the Chinese people, which had been proposed by some ethnic elites such as Li Shixian, Wang Tao, Sun Yat-sen, Tang Caichang and Liang Qichao, and

the generalization and perfection of its concept and connotation should had been attributed to Liang Qichao.

Nation, it refers to a group of people objectively distinguished from other groups in culture, language and history, a concept formed through the study of human evolutionary history and race in modern times, a stable community formed through long-term historical development, a group that was distinguished from other groups based on history, culture and language, and accompanied by social progress. Economic development and the advancement of culture, language and civilization had led to the gradual integration and formation of related tribes living in the same area. The modern concept of the nation could be a group of people who were distinguished by the country, or it could only refer to a group of people who had a common cultural concept without a common language or historical source. In modern times, the same people might had different religious beliefs; The same people could also had different historical origins, and different people could use the same language.

3. ORIGIN OF HAN NATIONALITY IN CHINA

China was an ancient country, with thousands or even tens of thousands of years of civilization history, but it was customary to say that 5,000 years of Chinese civilization history, this history was part of the birth history of "China". Han nationality was the largest ethnic group in China at present. Before the concept of nationality had been formed, it had been called Han people. The title of Han people probably began in the early Han Dynasty, which originally meant people of Han Dynasty and was the name given to Han people by people in Xiongnu and other Non-Han regime areas.

From the beginning, the name of the Han people had inherited all the ethnic groups in China from Qin Dynasty, and Qin Dynasty had inherited all the ethnic groups in Zhou Dynasty, and Zhou Dynasty had inherited all the ethnic groups in Shang Dynasty, and Shang Dynasty had inherited all the ethnic groups in Xia Dynasty. In this way, we could find that the ancestors of the Han people are the living tribal clans in the Yellow River Valley and the Yangtze River Valley during the period of the Three Emperors and five emperors of China. We usually call the Huaxia people. It could be seen that the composition of the original Han people was extremely complex, and some Han people were the ancestors of many later Chinese minorities. With the evolution of The Times and history, the Han people had also been divided, and some branches had evolved into the later Chinese minorities, and even the current nationalities of other countries.

In the Chinese language, Han referred to both Han people and Han residents. Nationality was not a biological concept, but a historical concept and a process concept. Nationality was gradually formed and had evolved in the historical process of human development, and its composition and attributes were not immutable, but develop and change with history. The same was true of the Han and other Chinese nationalities. In the process of formation and development, people of different blood relations, different tribes and even different races were integrated into the Han nationality. In the long history, many original ethnic groups had merged with other ethnic groups, and eventually had formed the largest ethnic group with the largest population in the world. Its evolution history reflected the great feat of the integration of Chinese nation.

4. EVOLUTION OF HAN NATIONALITY

Analyzing the evolution history of Han nationality with the passage of time and the pace of historical development, we will find that Han nationality would be the most integrated and absorbable nation in the world, and also the most capable of peaceful integration of ethnic groups. In the long history of formation and development, Han nationality peacefully had absorbed many tribes, nations and races.

4.1 Han Nationality Originated from Huaxia Nationality

The predecessor of Chinese Han was Chinese Huaxia (this was also the name of people later, in ancient times may only would

been called the Huaxia tribe, Yan-Huang Clan-tribe), and the source of Huaxia, its origin could be traced back to Yan-Huang clan-tribal group, according to the earliest historical had recorded, more than 4000 years ago, China had haven Yan Emperor, Yellow Emperor and Chiyou three Clan-tribes. After the Yan Huang War and the Yellow Emperor Chiyou War, the Yellow Emperor tribe became the final victor, and the Yan Huang tribe and a part of Chiyou's tribe merged to become the core of the primitive Huaxia. Another section of Chiyou fled south and became Sanmiao, mixing with other local tribes in the Yangtze Valley^[2].

Huaxia tribe had begun to form in Xia Dynasty, and Shang Dynasty had destroyed the summer, which unified the two major tribal groups in the middle and lower reaches of the Yellow River into a whole. The origin of the word "Hua" and "Xia" of the Huaxia nationality had lain in the long history of "Hua" as the abbreviation of China. The ancient word "Hua" would be the same as "flower"^[3]. According to legend, people in the ancient Central Plains had worn very gorgeous and neat clothes. The word Hua also would have the meaning of red. People in ancient Zhou Dynasty had liked red and had regarded it as a symbol of good luck, which would be often referred to as "Chinese red". Since the Zhou people called themselves "Hua", many of the vassal states of the Zhou Dynasty had been called "Zhuhua". The commentary in Zuo's Spring and Autumn Annals said "Zhuhua, China"^[4]. However, the "summer" would refer to the Xia Dynasty, and some people said that the fiefdom of Qi-Xia administrative scope. Huaxia would come from China, the main blood line of fiefdom Xia was called Zhu Xia, Zhu Xia had formed Huaxia.

Five-Emperors era, Xia and Shang dynasties after Yan-Huang, the Huaxia had conquered and integrated some surrounding tribes. The Shang people from the east of Xia-Country had destroyed the Xia and established Shang Dynasty. At the same time, People in Shang Dynasty conquered many Eastern states. The residents of these kingdoms had been also integrated into the Huaxia, which would show that the Huaxia people would be already very complex during Shang Dynasty.

In the 11th century BC, Zhou people from the west had destroyed Shang State, and King Wu of the State Zhou had destroyed Shang Dynasty and established the Zhou Dynasty. The Zhou people were differentiated among the Qiang people in the west, and Zhou Dynasty made Zhou people, Xia people and merchants had appeared a great fusion. In Western Zhou Dynasty, the Huaxia ethnic name appeared, which was different from the Yi, Man, Rong and Di nationalities^[5]. It could be seen that the Huaxia people before Zhou Dynasty were the collective name of the tribes living in the Yellow River valley of ancient China, and Zhou people flowed merchants into the Xia Dynasty to form the Huaxia, which was the iron proof of national integration. On the other hand, it could be seen that Yi Nationality, Barbarian Nationality, Rong Nationality and Di Nationality, which were different from Huaxia Nationality, were actually the ethnic minorities formed when Shang Dynasty nobility had not done want to submit to the Zhou Dynasty regime and led their tribes to leave the Yellow River valley far away from the Area ruled by Zhou Dynasty. It could be seen from this that all ethnic groups in China would be originally one.

4.2 Development of Han Nationality

Han nationality began with Huaxia nationality, and Huaxia nationality was also evolving with the changes of The Times, not unchanged, on-off, on-off, on-off, on-off, on-off.

According to the Records of the Grand Historian, the ancestors of Xiongnu people were Xia Dynasty. After Xia Dynasty had been destroyed by Shang Dynasty, some Xia people did not want to be ruled by Shang Dynasty, so they fled north, and finally fled to the northern grasslands. After arriving on the grassland, these Xia Dynasty remnants began to integrate with some nomadic peoples on the grassland, and finally formed Xiongnu nation. It could be seen that Xiongnu and Han people originated from Huaxia nationality.

Han nationality originated from Han people, Han people were the people of Han Dynasty, and the residents under the rule of Han Dynasty. They were the people inherited from Qin people and other Six States and the descendants of the princes and ministers of various states, etc. They also accepted nomadic ethnic minorities near various countries or foreign people flowing into

Han territory, such as Hunnu people in the reign of Emperor Wudi of Han Dynasty, Hunnu and Hun Evil King in the West and other five major groups surrendered to Han Dynasty. Their descendants were integrated into the Hans.

Han nationality was fully developed in the powerful Han Dynasty, which was another unified state in Chinese history after Qin Dynasty and was a powerful country in the world alongside the Roman Empire at that time. After the establishment of Han Dynasty, starting from Emperor Wudi of Han, Western Han Dynasty penetrated the Western regions, conquered Xiongnu, flattened Xiqiang, conquered Korea, conquered Southwest Yi, conquered Minyue and Nanyue, and made various contacts with the surrounding ethnic minorities with unprecedented frequency. In these exchanges, other nationalities began to call the Han army "Han soldiers", the envoys sent to other countries were called "Han ambassadors", the people living in the Han region were called "Han people", and the name "Han nation" was basically established.

4.3 Hard to Survive in Maelstrom of War Caused by Five Ethnic Peoples

After the decline of Han Dynasty, the Central Plains were in war, the economy was backward, and the people had no livelihood. Some Han people left the Han homeland and fled to other places to survive. On the other hand, with the rise of other ethnic regimes around Han Dynasty, Xiongnu and Donghu, which existed in the Yin and Shang Dynasties, split into Xianbei and Wuhuan under the continuous would attack of Xiongnu in North and Northeast China. During Han Dynasty, the Southern Xiongnu had annexed to Han Dynasty, and the Northern Xiongnu had retreated to the north under the attack of the Han Army, while Xianbei gradually grew stronger and Wuhuan had been destroyed by the Wei of The Three Kingdoms and merged into the Wei and became the Han people.

During the period of Returning to Jin from the Three Kingdoms, the Xiongnu basically had disappeared (some of them fled to the north, and the rest were classified into the Han), and Xianbei had grown unprecedentedly. During Jin Dynasty, Xianbei had been divided into three tribes: East, North and west. The North Xianbei (Tuoba Xianbei) had become the main part of Xianbei and had been extremely prosperous and powerful. Under the leadership of Murong Clan, Xixianbei had moved to Qinghai and had changed into Tuyuhun.

At the end of Jin Dynasty, the five Hu tribes (mainly Xiongnu, Xianbei, Ji, Qiang and Di, but in fact, the Five Hu were the representatives of the chaotic Huahu people at the end of Western Jin, the number was far from five) were in chaos, and many nomads outside Western Jin Dynasty took advantage of the chaos of the eight Kings of Western Jin and their national strength was weakened, and successively established several Non-Han regimes, forming a period of confrontation with the southern regime. During this period, the Han people were slaughtered and almost wiped out in some places in the north. Part of the Han people fled south and crossed the Yellow River and Yangtze River (the Southern crossing) to establish the Eastern Jin Dynasty, which allowed them to survive. China also entered the most turbulent period of 130 years. After more than 100 years of war, some ethnic minority regimes disappeared, and finally attributed to the Northern Wei Dynasty in the north (Xianbei Tuoba was founded), Ji was almost completely destroyed, most of the Qiang and Di were subdivided into Han Nationality, a few moved into the Qinghai-Tibet Plateau and became the later Tubo, most of Xianbei was Sinicized by itself, and some spread to other countries and became other ethnic groups. The 169-year history of China had entered the Southern and Northern Dynasties, which was a huge era of national integration in China, although this integration was barbaric and civilized. In the end, the Han people had struggled to survive in this dark and war-torn era, and had continued to pass on their own blood and inherit Han culture.

4.4 Rise abruptly of Sui and Tang Dynasties

The rise and strength of the Sui and Tang dynasties were inseparable from the role played by Han culture. The ancestors of the Kaijiang royal family in the Sui Dynasty were Xianbei, who took the initiative to integrate into the Han nationality, and the Longxi Guanzhong Group was also an excellent representative of Xianbei's initiative to integrate into the Han nationality. The

Han nationality in the Sui and Tang Dynasties was no longer the original Han nationality, but the Han nationality injected fresh blood, and the Xianbei in history had disappeared and completely integrated into the Han nationality. The Han nationality of the Sui Dynasty was already the new Han nationality, and the subsequent Tang Dynasty was even more integrated with other ethnic groups (integrating Turkic tribes and other nationalities). The rise of Han Nationality in the Sui and Tang Dynasties was manifested in the following aspects: 1) The rulers of Sui and Tang Dynasties were actually New Han Nationality, which had been integrated into Han Nationality by other nationalities. 2) In Sui and Tang Dynasties, Han culture had reached its peak, and other nationalities had taken great pride in learning Han culture. In Sui and Tang Dynasties, with the development of commerce and the prosperity of spiritual civilization, cultural diversity gradually emerged. In Sui Dynasty, the culture of Southern Dynasty had been absorbed, and in Tang Dynasty, the Renaissance made Buddhism, Taoism, Islam and other pagan ideas emerge. The culture of the noble people stood opposite to the culture of the common people, and the farming culture and nomadic culture integrated. In other words, Han culture would be still the mainstream culture in China, but Chinese culture had developed in the direction of diversity and complexity. 3) From the perspective of geographical location, economic development and social structure, the Han nationality had always occupied the central position. However, in politics, economy, culture and other aspects, the integration and communication of various nationalities had begun to appear, and the politics, economy, culture and other aspects of Sui and Tang Dynasties had reflected the characteristics of pluralism, rather than a single phenomenon of Han centralization.

4.5 Ups and downs after Tang Dynasty

After the fall of Tang Dynasty, the history of China in Five Dynasties and Ten States had ushered in another era of fragmentation, war and turbulence, during which a half-century, China had occurred the emergence of Liao, later Liang, later Tang, Later Jin and later Han and other regimes. The rise and fall of these regimes were often accompanied by wars and regime changes. The fate of Han people in this era had been closely related to the fate of China and the alternation of various regimes, wars and belonging. Some Han people under the control of Liao, Later Liang, Later Tang, Later Jin, Later Han and other regimes had joined or integrated into ethnic minorities. The fate of Han people who did not integrate into ethnic minorities had been closely related to the political quality and moral character of those who ruled the ethnic minorities.

The subsequent Song Dynasty, with its parallel regimes such as Liao, Xia, Jin and Mongolia, had been highly developed economically and culturally, but had suffered from numerous military and diplomatic setbacks and failures.

During Yuan Dynasty, although it was less than a hundred years, the fate of Han people was miserable, and Han Culture was almost wiped out. Under the brutal rule of the Yuan and Mongolia, the peasants rose up and overthrew the Yuan rule in just a few years, and then the Han regime of Ming Dynasty had been established.

Ming Dynasty would be a feudal dynasty re-established by Han people on Chinese soil. The establishment of Ming Dynasty had improved the status of Han people, made the majority of Han people back to the status of the common people, and had created favorable conditions for the further development of China in the future. The greatest contribution of Ming Dynasty to the development of Han people would be to integrate the region under its rule into the only Han people, to reunite Southern Han people with the northern Han people, and in its heyday, to extend Han people into what was now Vietnam. The contribution of Ming Dynasty to the integration of the ethnic groups would be that it did not separate the ethnic groups.

During Qing Dynasty, Han Nation would be also ravaged and oppressed. During the establishment of Qing Dynasty, almost all Han people had been killed. The three slaughtering events in Jiading and the Ten days in Yangzhou had been covered with the criminal blood stains of genocide and bloody massacres.

4.6 Peculiarity

The evolution of Han people would be a long and arduous history. As a biological being, Han people would be the main

body of China's evolution history, the main body and main contributor to the creation of Chinese civilization and culture, and the main direction of the whole Chinese nation, playing a leading and decisive role. According to the genetic studies of different ethnic groups in the world conducted by scholars around the world in recent years, almost all of them had reached similar conclusions about Han Nationality, that was, although there were regional differences in Han Nationality, the differences between different regions were very small on the whole, and in many aspects, they were similar to the internal differences of some small ethnic groups with millions or even tens of millions of people^[5]. It also would reflected the historical exchanges between North China and West Asia through the Silk Road, South China and the Qinghai-Tibet Plateau, and South Asia through the Maritime Silk Road. Therefore, on the whole, this shows that the genes of today's Han Nationality came from the ancient Han Nationality, and Han Nationality would be a blood and cultural nationality with the main genes of the ancient Han nationality as the main body, and at the same time, it would integrated a large number of neighboring nationalities and other ethnic origins in history. It would be not only a descent from ancient times to modern times, but also a cultural ethnic group that integrates a large number of North Asia, Central Asia, South Asia and even West Asia.

5. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

From the historical analysis of the evolution and development of Han Nation, it could be seen that the concept of Han Nation was only clearly put forward at the end of Qing Dynasty, calling Han people began in Han Dynasty, but the blood of Han people could be traced back to the Huaxia called by the Yin and Shang, and then could be traced back to Yan-Huang Tribe, and continue to go deeper and go back to the Cherien of the Three Emperors.

However, the descendants of Cheren Clan were scattered all over the world, and Yan-Huang Clan was only one of its descendants, while Huaxia Clan was also one of the descendants of Yan-Huang Clan, and Han people in the Han Dynasty were only one of the descendants of Huaxia Clan. It could be seen that the Rong Di, Fengfang and Shanrong of Han D ynasties and Zhou Dynasties, LinHu, ChangDi, YiQu and QuanRong of the Warring States period, etc. The Xionggnu, Donghu, Yueshi in Western Han Dynasty, Xianbei, Xionggnu, Ji and Di in Northern and Southern Dynasties, Tubo and Rouran in Sui Dynasty, Khitan and Dangxiang in Northern Song Dynasty, and Jurchen, Dangxiang and Mongols in Southern Song Dynasty all had been originated from Huaxia Nationality, which would show that all ethnic groups on the land of China have the same root.

In the long history of the development of Han Nationality, not only Rongdi, Funfang, Shanrong, Linhu, Changdi, Yiqu, Xionggnu, Rouran, Tujic, Xianbei, Ji, Di, Tangxiang and Kidan, Mongolia and Jurzhen and other minorities, but also Arabs from Persia and other foreign nationalities. Similarly, today's Mongolian, Manchu, Hui, Uyghur, Miao, Zhuang, etc., were all once integrated into the Han tribe or Han, or originally developed from the branch of the Han.

It could be seen from the origin and development history of Han nationality that there was no absolute concept, absolute connotation and absolute extension of any ethnic group. The concept and connotation of the ethnic group change with the change of time and space, and the development and evolution of the floating in the long river of history. Han Nationality and Mongolian, Manchu, Hui, Uyghur, Miao, Zhuang and other ethnic minorities in China were interdependent. There's me in you, there's you in me, there was no absolute distinction and difference, blood compatibility, the same root, the same ancestor. Therefore, the evolution history of the Han reflects the great integration of the Chinese nation, the integration of the Chinese nation as a whole, the unification of the same nation - the Chinese nation (or Chinese) theory would be sufficient, conclusive evidence, completely feasible, and very necessary and important and urgent.

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